

IMPROVING THE SAFETY STANDARDS OF BULK RESERVOIRS**Bakiev Masharif Ruzmetovich**

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Annotation:An artificial reservoir built to collect and store water using dams. The universal reservoir meets the needs of several sectors of the national economy (irrigation, water supply, electricity, shipping, fishing, flood control, etc.). Changes in river flow during the year and its uneven distribution over the territory necessitate the construction of a reservoir. The reservoir regulates the flow seasonally and annually, along with channels and other water distribution facilities allows for regional redistribution. Depending on the location of the basin, it is divided into a reservoir in the riverbed (the dam blocks the riverbed and part of the flow in the valley) and a reservoir that is filled (a natural or artificial pool is used outside the riverbed). . The main structures in the reservoir are a dam (blocking water), a spillway (water supply to water users) and a spillway (removal of excess water). In addition to this, the reservoir will also have dams, inlet and outlet channels bounding the basin..

Turbidity of the reservoir is very dangerous. In some cases, the tank will completely fail due to filling with turbidity. The siltation process is caused by sedimentation after the construction of a dam on the river. The main sources of biogenic elements are turbidity of water, soil, products of wind and water erosion. The reservoir in Central Asia is very quickly covered with turbidity. For example, the Chimkurgan reservoir built in Kashkadarya will cost 60 million in 20 years. m3, Pachkamarskoe

reservoir in Guzordarya. 17 million in 9 years. m³, a quarter of the South Surkhan reservoir has been filled with silt for 25 years; The volume of the Uchkurgan reservoir in the Syr Darya has decreased by 60 in 19 years%i.

Key words: Reservoir, Dam, Erosion, Flood, Destruction, Level, Wall, Pool, Degradation, Drainage.

Introduction

Reservoirs to be filled are built by filling natural depressions and hollows located outside the riverbed. If the depressions are not deep enough, they are surrounded by dams or increase the water capacity by deepening the bottom. Since they are located outside the riverbed, water is supplied through special channels. For example, the Tolimarzhan reservoir in Kashkadarya region is filled with water from the Amu Darya through the Karshi main canal, and the Uchkizil reservoir in Surkhandarya region is filled with water from Surkhandarya through the Zangi Canal. Examples of this type include Karkidon in the Fergon Valley, Kuimozor, Tudakol reservoirs in the Bukhara region. Tanks are considered "structures containing dangerous forces." international humanitarian law because of their possible negative impact. The break of the Banqiao Reservoir dam in 1975 and other dams in Henan Province, China, resulted in more casualties than any other dam break in history.

As a result of the natural disaster, about 171,000 people died[1], and 11 million were left homeless. Because reservoirs and their dams pose such a great potential danger, many countries have adopted legislation and established safety standards, but it was only in the 1930s that dams and reservoirs were first designed, built and put into operation. rendering services to them. The Reservoirs (Safety Regulations) Act 1930 was passed in the UK..

Although a breakout is often described as a catastrophic failure of the dam wall to hold the water mass behind the reservoir, there are several other important reasons for the breakout. This includes the following:

This is a reservoir that stores water and makes it possible to use it in the future. The general appearance of reservoirs, catchment conditions and methods of dam construction are different. According to these signs, they can be divided into the following groups: - closed reservoirs; - open reservoirs. Closed tanks include large and small water storage tanks and reservoirs. Such tanks are made of iron, reinforced concrete, stone and other materials. They are designed to manage spending by day, week, month, and sometimes by season. Cisterns that have long existed in our country can also be attributed to the type of reservoirs. There are two types of open reservoirs: 1. Dam reservoirs; 2. Reservoirs with dams. Reservoirs with dams are found in the following forms: a) a one-sided dam built on a slope to protect against floods; b) a circular dam built in a horizontal place; c) a half-dug dam, a reservoir is being built in order to increase the water capacity. The aforementioned reservoirs can be used for different purposes and, depending on this, their tasks are also different. It is known that in most cases reservoirs are built by building dams in river valleys. Reservoirs of this type are the most common and are of great importance in the national economy.

Dams of reservoirs are divided into two types according to their purpose: a) dams designed to maintain the water level. Are built for the purposes of energy, water transport, water intake from a river or canal; b) dams built to collect water and regulate the flow of the river. Nowadays, it is rare to build a dam for one purpose. Most nodes are created for complex purposes.

- Insufficient barrier causes water to seep into the dam wall and flow down the unprotected wall, causing erosion and eventually collapse
- The dam is not sufficiently connected to the bedrock, which allows it to slip out from under the dam wall, which leads to erosion and erosion of the dam.
- Adequate construction of geological exploration, allowing water to move further away from the dam and destroy the new outlet channel.
- Insufficient construction spillage leading to erosion and degradation of the barrier surface due to regular leaching.

- Geological subsidence due to poor geology, mining or oil production.
- Insufficient drainage pipe capacity due to clogging or corrosion.
- Inadequate design for actual precipitation

Above mentioned indicators, it can be said that measures to improve the safety of operation of bulk reservoirs are described.

Materials

The safety and reliability of liquid reservoirs is an indicator determined depending on its technical performance and classification. The main indicators of reservoirs. Indicators (parameters) of reservoirs are determined in two directions: - parameters characterizing the size of the reservoir: - parameters determining the mode of use of the reservoir: The first type, that is, parameters characterizing the size of the reservoir of reservoirs, are as follows: a) standard humidity level (NDV); b) useless volume level (FHS); c) working water level (MPV). The normal humidity level (UVV) is the level at which the dam can hold the water stored in it for a long time without damage when the reservoir is filled to this level. The repeatability and continuity of the MDS depends on the flow regime of the river and the level of its management. With seasonal management of river flow, the MDS is achieved every year, and with multi—year management - only in high-water years. Useless Volume Level (FHS) - Part of the water stored in the tank above this level is used. The repeatability of PGO also depends on the flow regime of the river and the level of its management, PGO is observed annually with seasonal management of river flow, and with long-term management in low-water years - at the end of the fall. There are the following forms of water capacity - the size of reservoirs, and each of them has a specific task: a) useful volume or working volume (vf) b) useless or dead volume (bb) c) total or full volume (c)) g) working depth (hi). The useful or working volume is located between the MDS and the FCS. The flow of the river is mainly controlled by this volume..

Methods

In order to ensure the technical and operational safety of liquid reservoirs, various hydraulic measures can be implemented, including ensuring the proper functioning of drainage systems, ensuring the operation of emergency channels when the water level exceeds the accelerated level, the useful coefficient of drainage is high, it is planned to

implement the complexity of operation at the level of.

Figure 1. Schemes of the location of reservoirs.

Figure 2. The main elements and zones of the reservoir

The harmful consequences of building water reservoirs include: 1) areas where settlements, industrial enterprises, agricultural crops, forests, railways and highways, communication and electric networks, cultural and historical monuments, etc. are located are under water. stay; 2) temporary flooding of the territory of the banks of the reservoir in the range from the normal wetted level to the rapidly wetted level; 3) an unnecessary rise in the level of seepage water in the area around the reservoir; 4) reducing the size of existing under-bridge facilities required by special standards for water transport, etc.

Results

Problems arising after the construction of a hydraulic lock and measures to solve them. The creation of reservoirs on rivers is largely a positive factor, but they can also cause negative consequences that require special measures. No less important is the violation of the ecological relationship between the environment and the living world,

some of its manifestations are manifested in the relationship of existing reservoirs with surrounding lands, environmental protection of nature needs to take appropriate measures..

As a result of the construction of reservoirs in the habitat , the following violations occur: 1) changes in the landscape due to the transformation of the coast and coastal margins; 2) the formation of shallow and muddy zones; 3) flooding of the territory by some representatives of the animal and plant world; 4) loss of spawning grounds for some fish species; 5) "flowering" of reservoir water. To compensate for the damage caused by flooding and flooding, it is necessary to carry out the following measures: 1) relocation and restoration of urban, rural, industrial and agricultural enterprises that have fallen into the flood zone and in new places; 2) transfer of individual road sections, strengthening of their elevations, strengthening of slopes, transfer of communications and electrical networks, etc.; 3) lifting of bridge spans above, reconstruction of transitional bridges, construction of new ones bridges or driveways; 4) clearing the territory of the reservoir from trees and shrubs based on water transport, fisheries and sanitary-hygienic requirements, in the case of cutting down trees of rare species, planting them on another similar protected from flooding territory; 5) ensuring the possibility of mining (for example, coal, building materials, etc.) or their further production; 6) protection or relocation of historical and cultural monuments, as well as their study and inspection. Engineering principles. In some cases, it remains under the tank.

Discussion and conclusion

To reduce the negative impact on the environment during the construction of reservoirs, the following engineering and technical measures are used: 1) shore protection and shore protection measures; 2) to prevent shallowing and silting of the reservoir; 3) to conduct a preliminary ecological survey of the territory intended for flooding, with the identification and preservation of unique species of flora and fauna; 4) organization of fishing; 5) combating the "flowering" of water in the form of blue-

green algae using coastal floats, chemical reagents, water aeration, etc., etc. In addition, sanitary and hygienic requirements must be observed in the reservoir and its surroundings, it is forbidden to dump waste, sewage sludge into the reservoir, store instant, toxic substances on its shores, etc..

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